

Functional state and physical develop in boxers with different style of fight

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Abstract

Currently, in boxing, no scientifically substantiated provisions have been developed regarding the consideration of fighting style. In this regard, the present study aims to comparatively examine the features of functional capabilities and physical qualities, such as speed qualities, explosive endurance, and speed endurance, between boxers of offensive and defensive fighting styles. Regarding speed qualities, in offensive-style boxers, the increase in the number of punches within 8 seconds was 22% by the 2nd week of the training process and 37% by the 4th week. In the second group (defensive-style boxers), positive changes in the number of punches within 8 seconds were observed in the 2nd microcycle (17% increase), rising to 27% by the 4th microcycle. A similar trend was observed for another speed indicator—the number of punches within 40 seconds.

Regarding explosive endurance (IEE – Index of Explosive Endurance) in offensive-style boxers, the increase in IEE values was 11% by the 2nd week and reached 16% by the 4th week. Among defensive-style boxers, the IEE increase was 8% by the 2nd week and 10% by the 4th week.

The Speed Endurance Index (SEI) demonstrated significant positive changes for offensive-style boxers. By the 2nd microcycle, the SEI increase was 14%, reaching 22% by the 4th week. Among defensive-style boxers, the SEI increase was 6% by the 2nd microcycle and 8% by the 4th microcycle.

Keywords: functional state, physical develop, style of fight, boxers.

Introduction

The defining features of modern boxing are the high density of technical actions and intense confrontation throughout the bout (Niewczas et al., 2023; Beránek et al., 2023). These conditions impose specific requirements on athletes—they must be able to execute technical elements continuously under conditions of intense opposition, time constraints, and limited space (Folhes et al., 2022; Giboin et al., 2023). Moreover, it is necessary not only to increase the volume and variety of technical techniques but also to ensure multifaceted variability of these techniques, which constitute the foundation of boxing skills. Thus, improving athletic performance in boxing is impossible without integrating optimal methods of technical and tactical training into the training process (El-Ashker et al., 2018; Ponce-Bordón et al., 2022).

In recent years, Uzbek boxers have achieved significant success in international competitions, winning gold, silver, and bronze medals at the Olympic Games (2012, 2016, 2020), thus firmly establishing the advanced position of the Uzbek boxing school. The performance of the Uzbekistan national boxing team at the 2020 Tokyo Olympics has been analyzed, but the most phenomenal achievement was in 2024 at the XXXIII Olympic Games in Paris, where Uzbek boxers won 7 medals, including 5 gold, further strengthening Uzbekistan's position in world boxing.

Under these conditions, a scientifically grounded approach to training organization is required, ensuring a combination of intensive training with other types of activities while taking into account individual athlete characteristics. It is particularly important not only to assess the athlete's immediate physiological response to a given training load but also to develop the ability to predict and forecast performance outcomes (Hugues et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2024).

Considerable attention has been devoted to the scientific substantiation of combat sports training technologies, including boxing, at various stages of the training cycle, with a particular focus on the pre-competition period (Bozdarov et al., 2023; Korobeynikov et al., 2023).

The use of innovative technologies in training and mastering technical actions in complexly coordinated sports provides undeniable benefits for improving athletes' technical and tactical skills (Yuriy et al., 2014; Djurabevich et al., 2022). The authors determine the level of sports preparedness of a boxer based on such criteria as the number of accurate punches to the head and body, defensive, offensive, and counterattacking actions, as well as violations per round (Korobeynikov et al., 2023; Mansur et al., 2022).

It should be noted that the methods of developing special physical fitness in boxing are also widely applied in training special forces personnel (Lee et al., 2022). At the same time, in boxing, there are no scientifically substantiated provisions regarding the consideration of fighting styles, as well as the manifestation of speed qualities and endurance between boxers of offensive and defensive styles.

Purpose of the study

To study the functional differences and levels of physical qualities between boxers of offensive and defensive fighting styles.

Materials and Methods

The experiment involved 15 highly skilled boxers, who formed the experimental group (EG). The control group (CG) also consisted of 15 highly skilled boxers.

At the initial stage of the experiment, sport-technical indicators were measured, and fighting styles were determined. Additionally, an assessment of the physical development of both CG and EG boxers was conducted using anthropometric research methods. Based on physiological methods, specific functional changes caused by training influences were identified.

At the second stage of the study, an analysis of the structure of physical preparedness was carried out, along with the identification of priority boxing tactics and the arsenal of technical and tactical actions, which allowed for the determination of the fundamental characteristics of boxers with defensive and offensive fighting styles.

The presence of these specific characteristics necessitated the development and implementation of individualized training programs, incorporating varied means of technical and tactical preparation for both offensive and defensive-style boxers.

Results

It is well known that in sports, the style of competitive activity determines the tactics of conducting sports combat.

In combat sports, three fighting styles are distinguished: offensive (attacking), counterattacking (defensive), and combined styles (Korobeynikov et al., 2015). The results of the conducted research demonstrated that boxers with different fighting styles exhibit significant differences in temporal functional activity parameters. Specifically, among boxers with offensive and defensive fighting styles, statistically significant differences were identified in several functional indicators, whereas no differences were found in morphological characteristics.

Boxers who prefer an offensive fighting style exhibit shorter visual-motor reaction times (170.2 ± 4.2 ms) (Table 1) and higher accuracy in reaction to a moving object (520 ms). Conversely, boxers who employ a counterattacking fighting style demonstrate relatively longer simple motor reaction times (195.6 ± 7.5 ms) but greater stability in reaction accuracy to a moving object (530 ms).

Table 1 Morpho-functional indicators of skilled boxers with different fighting styles

№	Indicators	Offensive Style	Counterattacking Style	Statistical Significance
1	Body weight (kg)	66,5 ±11,15	67,5±11,3	P<0,05
2	Body height (cm)	176,0±8,28	176,7±9,54	P>0,05
3	MHI (Mass-Height Index)	380,1±48,74	379,9±45,95	P>0,05
4	Deadlift strength (kg)	170,7±18,7	162,7±12,52	P<0,05
5	Simple visual-motor reaction time (ms)	175,2±4,3	195,8±7,5	P<0,05
6	Accuracy reaction to a moving object (RMO) (ms)	520,3±6,1	530,6±2,5	P>0,05
7	Stange test – breath-holding time (s)	21,4±8,31	22,6±9,4	P>0,05

The Stange test, which measures breath-holding time, was used in our study. The results were similar: for offensive-style boxers, the breath-holding time was 21 seconds, whereas for defensive-style boxers, it was 22 seconds, which is considered a good indicator. Defensive or counterattacking boxers are predisposed to rapid responses in simple motor reaction tests, meaning they possess a heightened ability to perceive and process information quickly.

Considering that each fighting style involves distinct expressions of various physical and cognitive attributes, it can be assumed that each category of boxers differs not only in their individual functional capabilities but also in their preferred fighting techniques.

Analysis of Speed Qualities

We examined changes in speed qualities through specific tests, such as the number of punches executed within 8 seconds and 40 seconds. The tested athletes performed these computer-assisted tests, which were integrated into the specialized program "SNRJ – 20", developed in collaboration with the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan under the supervision of Professor S.S. Tadzhibaev.

The boxer performed punches for 8 seconds at maximum speed, followed immediately by 40 seconds of continuous striking without rest. The punches were executed on a specially suspended boxing bag, and the computer program automatically registered the strikes. The results provided data not only on speed qualities but also on explosive and speed endurance.

As shown in Table 2, offensive-style boxers delivered 41.7 ± 6.09 punches in 8 seconds and 82.9 ± 12.61 punches in 40 seconds. In contrast, defensive-style boxers delivered 34.5 ± 10.95 punches in 8 seconds and 68 ± 22.78 punches in 40 seconds.

The difference between the compared groups in the number of punches in 8 seconds was 17.3%, while the difference in the number of punches in 40 seconds was 18% in favor of offensive-style boxers (Table 2).

Table 2 Indicators of Special Work Capacity and Indices of Explosive and Speed Endurance in Boxers

Note: IEE – Index of Explosive Endurance; SEI – Speed Endurance Index

	Offensive Style $\bar{x} \pm \sigma$	Defensive Style $\bar{x} \pm \sigma$	Difference (%)	t	P
Number of punches – 8 sec	41.1±6,09	34.5±10.95	17,3	2,23	<0.05
Number of punches – 40 sec	82.9±12.61	68±22.78	18	2.22	<0.05
IEE – Index of Explosive Endurance	13.14±7,35	18.36±3,42	39,7	2,49	<0.05
SEI – Speed Endurance Index.	3.2±1.16	4,17±1.19	30,43	2,27	<0.05

Discussion

The primary objective of our study was to examine the functional differences and manifestation levels of physical qualities between boxers of offensive and defensive styles. For this purpose, methods for assessing the special work capacity of boxers were employed. The obtained results revealed differences in temporal and functional parameters among boxers with different fighting styles. Similar findings were reported by other researchers, who demonstrated that tempo-style boxers differ from representatives of other styles by having lower nervous system mobility but greater endurance in speed and precision actions (Kozin et al., 2022).

At the same time, our results indicate that between offensive and defensive-style boxers, significant differences in a number of functional indicators were identified, whereas no differences in morphological characteristics were found. This suggests that psychophysiological functions take precedence over morpho-functional parameters in boxers (Mosler et al., 2024).

Our findings establish that boxers who prefer an offensive fighting style demonstrate faster visual-motor reactions, accompanied by an increase in reaction accuracy. In contrast, boxers employing a counterattacking style exhibit longer reaction times, but at the same time, greater stability and precision in reacting to a moving object. This result aligns with previous research, which has shown that an offensive fighting style in combat sports is generally associated with faster reaction times, while a defensive style enhances the precision of

technical actions (Korobeynikov et al., 2021; Turlykhanov et al., 2022).

The assessment of special work capacity through tests measuring the number of punches in 8 seconds and 40 seconds established that offensive-style boxers delivered significantly more punches in 8 seconds compared to defensive-style boxers. A similar result was obtained for the 40-second punch test.

This finding indicates a higher level of special work capacity in offensive-style boxers. However, our results partially align with previous studies, which suggest that the number of punches executed by offensive boxers does not always correlate with their quality and effectiveness (Chwała et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2024).

Conclusion

The study obtained results related to various motor qualities, particularly speed qualities, explosive endurance, and speed endurance in boxers. An increase in speed qualities was observed in both groups of boxers, despite differences in quantitative indicators.

The analysis of the speed endurance index demonstrated significant positive changes in offensive-style boxers. Based on the level of special physical preparedness, scientifically grounded training programs with a sports-oriented focus for boxing can be developed.

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